

2007 Survey for the purseweb spiders *Sphodros niger* and *Sphodros rufipes*

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Abstract

In 2006 we caught two male purseweb spiders, *Sphodros niger* (Hentz), on Nantucket Island and we recorded dense populations of purseweb spider tubes belonging to what we have identified as *Sphodros rufipes* (Latreille) on Tuckernuck Island. *S. niger* is hard to find and understudied and *S. rufipes* is at its most extreme northern range on Tuckernuck. With support from the Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative, the Maria Mitchell Association, and the Tuckernuck Land Trust, we spent part of the summer in 2007 trapping for extremely cryptic *S. niger* on Nantucket in hopes of finding an area where we could uncover their tube webs. In addition to 336 pitfall trap-nights in three locations, we also completed five hours of searching in likely habitat for the tubes. We did not find any tubes but we did trap three more male specimens from two new locations and recorded an approximate wandering week in 2007 for the males of 6-14 June. We also accumulated 11 hours of search time in likely habitat looking for tubes of *S. rufipes* on Nantucket, without success. During a trip to Tuckernuck we repeated a 2006 survey of *S. rufipes* tubes and counted about 50 within 100 m². This tube density is very rare for the species and leads us to wonder if some of the tubes are *S. niger*. Whether *S. niger* occurs on Tuckernuck and *S. rufipes* on Nantucket and why *S. rufipes* is abnormally abundant on Tuckernuck remains unknown but this report provides the information needed so that for future work can answer these questions efficiently.

Background

Purseweb spiders (Mygalomorphae, Atypidae) build silken tubes that extend from underground to some attachment point above ground such as a tree trunk, rock, or concrete wall (Hardy 2003). They hunt from within the tubes and the only time they leave is when the male spiders wander in search of females for mating. For *Sphodros niger* (Hentz), wandering usually lasts for only about one week (Edwards and Edwards 1990). This is the only species that is widespread in the Northeast but it is also one of the most cryptic members of its family, building its tubes entirely under pine needles or leaf litter (Edwards and Edwards 1990). In 2006 we captured two male *Sphodros niger* on Nantucket in pitfall traps and found abundant webs of a southern species, *Sphodros rufipes* (Latreille), on Tuckernuck (Mckenna-Foster and Beaton 2007).

Finding large aggregations of either species is rare. In the literature, we have only found two instances where multiple *S. niger* tubes were found near each other (Beatty 1986; Edwards and Edwards 1990). All of these cases, however, describe the webs in very different habitats so

it is difficult to draw guidance from them. While we have not found *S. niger* tubes, we have located an area that may have a significant population.

Finding *S. rufipes* (Figs. 1 and 2) on Tuckernuck in 2006 was very exciting for several reasons. While it is more common in the literature, most likely because it builds more conspicuous tubes up tree trunks, none of the reports have recorded the tube densities we estimated for Tuckernuck (Poteat 1889; Hardy 2003). Additionally, in published literature, *S. rufipes* has not been documented north of Block Island (Gertsch and Platnick 1980). Its presence in such large abundance indicates that Tuckernuck may have a very unique population.

With support from the Nantucket Biodiversity Initiative (NBI) and the Maria Mitchell Association (MMA) and the Tuckernuck Land Trust (TLT) we designed a project to locate new populations of both *S. niger* and *S. rufipes* on Nantucket, find aggregations of *S. niger* silken tubes, and record a date for male wandering behavior for that species. We also aimed to trap for *S. niger* on Tuckernuck as well as re-affirm our identification of *S. rufipes* on that island.

Methods

We set nine pitfall traps in Sanford Farm and nine pitfall traps in Squam Swamp on Nantucket from 6 June 2007 to 19 June 2007 (Map 1). We trapped *S. niger* in both of these areas in 2006. We completed five hours of ground searching in known population areas to locate webs and set an additional four pitfalls in likely habitat in the Pout Ponds area. We also collected sightings and specimens from members of the community.

Pitfall traps consisted of an eight-ounce canning jar with a 14 cm diameter funnel hot-glued to the screw-on top following a design used by Robert Edwards on Cape Cod. The trap was buried so the lip of the funnel was flush with ground level and was covered with half of a plastic four gallon temporary landscaping pot (cut longitudinally) to protect it from rain. We used propylene glycol in the traps.

We used descriptions from Edwards and Edwards (1990) to guide our ground search effort. This entailed crawling on the ground and gently sweeping aside the grass and leaf litter and lifting up logs and rocks while looking for the dirty brown silk of the *S. niger* tubes. Edwards and Edwards originally located their first tube by lifting up a rotting board after multiple intense searches. We focused our searches in areas where we had caught a wandering male either in 2006 or 2007. Pine stands west of the Pout Ponds area were targeted with the four extra pitfall traps because of suitable habitat consisting of a deep pine duff layer on gentle slopes (Edwards and Edwards 1990).

Results

Sphodros niger

We caught three new specimens of *S. niger* and only one was a result of this specific study. In the 336 total trap nights across the island we caught one male in Squam Swamp between 6-10 June (Map 1). In a separate study involving 130 trap nights over the same time period in the Smooth Hummocks Coastal Preserve (SHCP) near the Miacomet Golf Course, we caught another male between 12 June and 19 June (Mckenna-Foster and Beaton 2008). The third male specimen came from ten-year-old islander, Blaise Flegg, who set a pitfall trap during the first week of June in his backyard on Exeter St. (Tom Nevers).

We searched the area around the Squam Swamp and Sanford Farm traps for one hour each. We completed two hours of searching around the SHCP pitfall traps and an additional hour in the State Forest area between the western junction of Polpis Rd. and Milestone Rd. None of these searches uncovered *S. niger* webs.

Due to weather and logistical problems, we were not able to trap on Tuckernuck during June. However, during a trip to the island from 29-31 July 2007, we spent one hour looking for *S. niger* tubes in likely habitat but did not locate any.

Sphodros rufipes

During that same trip to Tuckernuck, we found populations of *S. rufipes* in several more locations. In one area of low grasses in a pine stand we counted over 50 webs in 100 m². Every tube we found was attached vertically to grass or dead sticks between 11-15 cm above the ground surface (Fig. 3). We did not excavate any tubes or collect any specimens.

We have not found any evidence of this species on Nantucket despite over 11 hours of combined searching in habitats similar those on Tuckernuck.

Discussion

Sphodros niger

We were unable to find any *S. niger* webs and we were unable to determine if both species coexist on either island. However, the pitfall trapping succeeded in narrowing down the wandering date for *S. niger* males on Nantucket in 2007 as between 6 June and 19 June. In 2006, of two male specimens found, only one could be associated with an accurate date of 14 June. Though Edwards and Edwards (1990) report that the week *S. niger* males wander on Cape Cod varies unpredictably between the first and third week of June, we can assume that the best time to trap for males on Nantucket is between 6 June and 19 June skewed toward 9-14 June.

The most likely location for *S. niger* may be Squam Swamp since that is the only site where we have caught two specimens. Beaton also observed wandering males in the area several years ago.

Is *S. niger* rare on Nantucket or have we just caught males wandering far from their population centers? Edwards and Edwards (1990) only found tubes in an area on Cape Cod with thick pine duff, a characteristic that none of our successful trap sites exhibit. The Sanford Farm and SHCP sites are both open grassland, though each is near dense trees and each has a relatively thick litter layer (Black Cherry (*Prunus serotina*) leaves and dead grass debris respectively). The Squam Swamp site is a very wet forest with a relatively thin layer of leaf litter (personal observation).

In 2008, we will redouble our efforts and focus on live pitfall trapping and visual searches from 6 June through 19 June. There is no way to know exactly when the males will emerge and recent extremes in seasonality (i.e. a very long and warm fall in 2007, personal observations) may change it in either direction.

Future work should also involve trapping for *S. niger* on Tuckernuck. In our literature search we found only one paper describing both *S. niger* and *S. rufipes* populations in the same area (Kansas) (Morrow 1984). In that study, *S. niger* is described as twice as abundant as *S. rufipes*. If both species are found on Tuckernuck it would be an ideal opportunity to document them together.

Sphodros rufipes

We've identified this species based on female specimens (Fig. 1), the characteristics of the web/tube structure (Fig. 3) and reported sightings and pictures of the easily identified males (Fig. 2), but the identification of all of the upright tubes on Tuckernuck remains in doubt until we find out if *S. niger* occurs there. Morrow (1984) reported the tentative identifications of upright tubes similar to the Tuckernuck tubes as belonging to *S. niger*. However, we follow the descriptions of *S. niger* tubes on Cape Cod, which Edwards and Edwards (1990) state lie horizontally on the ground under pine duff. Additionally, other descriptions of *S. rufipes* tubes match those on Tuckernuck (Gertsch and Platnick 1980; Hardy 2003).

The species seems to be widely dispersed across Tuckernuck grassland and often the webs are in small aggregations, although single webs are not uncommon. The density of these aggregations (over 50 in 100 m²) is very unusual. They are 15 times higher than any previous reports we have found (Poteat 1889, 3.97/100m²; Hardy 2003, 1.3/100m²). Additionally, all other reported populations attach their tubes to trees or rocks while the tubes on Tuckernuck are all attached to grass or dead sticks despite proximity to trees. This may suggest that some or all of these tubes belong to *S. niger* but documentation of the males is needed to be sure. If observations in early June show large abundances of wandering *S. niger* males in these large tube aggregations the situation will be more clear.

Based on specific searched in 2007 and general spider searches from 2006 and 2007, we conclude that *S. rufipes* on Nantucket is very rare or isolated with a very remote possibility that it does not occur on the island at all. There are several possible explanations for its abundance on Tuckernuck and virtual absence on Nantucket. The most likely reasons may be a negative response to human disturbance and/or differing food availability between the islands.

A detailed survey of the *S. rufipes* population on Tuckernuck needs to be completed and published. Why are they so abundant? Do populations exist in habitats other than grassland? Future work will involve carefully mapping one of the tube aggregations and recording habitat structure and food availability. We also hope to create a distribution map for Tuckernuck based on point counts from across the island.

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Figure 1. Female *S. rufipes* from Tuckernuck 26-27 August 2006. The tube has been removed from the ground and found to contain hatchling spiders. The spider is about 4 cm in length. Picture taken by Cheryl Comeau-Beaton.

Figure 2. Male *S. rufipes* from Tuckernuck around July 3. *S. niger* males look similar except all the legs are black. Picture taken by Cheryl Creighton of the Tuckernuck Land Trust.

C. Comeau-Beaton

Figure 3. *S. rufipes* tube from Tuckernuck found in dense grass on a south facing slope on the southeastern side of the island. This tube contained a female.

Map 1. Locations of *Sphodros* sp. captures and areas sampled for them in 2006 and 2007.